
HISTORICAL SUSTAINABLE CITY-REGION FROM THE PAST TO THE PRESENT

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Abstract: *The city-region faced a group of varied problems throughout history. Such problems affected the level of sustainability and achievement of sustainable regional development. There is great need to study such phenomena and derive benefits. The major problems relate to the form of city-regions, the relation interaction between rural and urban areas, the physical pattern points of view, the occupational dynamics of city population, and the potentials of city-regions to support the settlers.*

The phenomena of formation/ emergence of cities could be studied with two eras. The first era is old regionalism divided into pre-industrial revolution and industrialization stage and technological Renaissance phase while the second era is the new regionalism.

Characterizes the city-region with simplicity and high level of sustainability with limited concept of capacity in pre-industrial revolution while the manufacturing stage of industrialization leads to increase the boundaries intervention within the city-region and diversity of its forms and Entering into environmental resource depletion phase.

Technological Renaissance stage tried to absorb the damage caused by the industrialization by use of modern technology but conversely the resource depletion and pollution rates had increased and there was a different developmental levels For the city-regions due to the increase in the international trade and emergence of global cities which appeared clearly in new regionalism stage; there was a requirement for rehabilitating the city-region for the global competition besides existence of global development policies to ease pressures on all sectors of development. These led to the emergence of phenomena like urban ruralization and reverse migration and emergence of highly complex patterns of spatial and economic relations between the city-regions.

Key Words: *Sustainable city-region, Capacity of city-region, Sustainability, city-region form, city-region pattern, global city-region, and city-region functions.*

1. INTRODUCTION

The city-region marked as a developmental level cleared the relations between urban and rural areas which in turn led to the sustainable regional development.

The success of sustained development of city-region considered a success in achieving the sustainable regional development, but to do that, we needed to follow the trends of sustainability through the history to put the basis for the future.

By using historical analysis, we could explore the city-region up to the new regionalism, reading all changes which happened at all aspects and would deduct all arguments that led to achievement of the sustainable development at the city-region level.

2. THE CITY AND ITS ROLE AS ORGANIC CONCEPT FOR ITS REGION

- Jefferson mentioned the core idea of the city, it served a related area.
- The city did not appear by itself; the historical background of the most cities stressed that there was a rural hinterland surplus production. It led to establishment of a business transaction to do the central functions.
- The origin and the function of the city to do the regional role and the regional land uses were the main reasons for the emergence of cities.
- The cities emerged to play a regional role to serve a related rural within its influence area (Amin, 1989).
- The city was the area of cultural evolution and technological advancement which integrated activities sometimes compete and complement and were all activities, services and science parks for scientists to present research to serve Cultural and scientific progress and introduce it to urban and rural areas and the climate of evolution was not available in the countryside and in the city it was necessary to study the territory of this city that had become the heart of this globe (Ibrahim, 1993).

3. THE CONCEPT OF CITY-REGION

- Dickinson,(1964) define as; It is a space with a mutual reliability relations between the main urban settlement and the related rural settlements, because the economic relations and mutual trade beside social service connections which rely on the city, besides the daily work trips between the city and the other settlements in its region.

- Jason Ranko, (2006) developed a definition as; it was an area that combines urban settlement and rural settlements, including economic, social and environmental relationships within 100,000 inhabitants as population size within the geographical scope of the downtown to the maximum depth within 30 to 60 km, in this range the communities were gatherings under social and economic characteristics.

Understanding the regional nature should consider the following:

- The regional city size and its relations with the other settlements within the region.
- The ratio of city size to the total of urban and rural settlements population size within the city-region.
- The city-region different from another with its area, the number of people, geographic conditions, the availability of the economic resources and the technical advancement besides the diversity of transportation methods.
- Study the distribution of work zones in the city and its region together and the ration for each settlement.
- Traffic planning in the city-region between the main city and its surrounding settlements or between themselves, besides determination of the public and private transportation methods in the regional traffic with specific role, ratio, and properties(Kamal, 1991).
- The relationship between the expansion of the city-region and travel time between home and work for either Town dwellers and residents of its region as a planning constraint for dimensions of the city-region.
- Study of land use and its distribution ratio and per capita for the city and its region.

4. THE IMPORTANCE OF STUDYING THE CITY-REGION

- The city-region is the most appropriate planning level which allow spatial control of land use for development whatever for economic, social or environmental development.
- Accommodate direct and indirect global variables and dealt with environmental impacts and translated for spatially distributed projects and activities according to the possibilities and constraints for urban development.
- The city-region is the bridge of institutional interaction between the regional and local institutes which helped to direct the formal economic activities and dropped the informal activities.

- The city-region planning helped to capture the aspects of urban expansions in large and medium-sized cities at the expense of agricultural and rural areas which had often high economic value.
- Urban and economic relations appear in a physical form which the measurement, evaluation, follow-up and monitor the variables making it easier to measure indicators of sustainable regional development.
- The city-region is the best planning level from which we could determine the urban capacity and the capacity of the resources and activities at the regional level.
- Using the city-region as an analytical unit in urban studies, increase the developmental dimensions due to the instability of the spatial extent of cities.
- Narrowing the sharpness of developmental inequalities and disparities between the city and the settlements within the extent of its influence, don't achieve with the individual studies but with planning study on city-region level.
- The launch of several European and American research programs and to update the sustainable regional planning policies at the level of city-regions, especially that witness urban expansion was one of the most important proofs of the importance of planning at the level of city-regions.

5. CITY-REGION DURING THE ERA OF OLD REGIONALISM

This stage can be divided into three phases, namely the pre-industrial revolution and industrialization and technological Renaissance stage.

5.1 Sustainability of the city-region in pre-industrial revolution (stage of simplicity and uncomplicated)

5.1.1 The form of city-region

- Lack of functional specialization could be seen in pre-industrial stage.
- City was of small size due to several factors like technological simplicity. This stage had passed with different periods of pre-agricultural and agricultural, after that, stages of markets and trade exchange. The city region emerged in simple and uncomplicated form as mentioned here:
 - 1- Pre-agricultural settlements which were distinct with small size of population spread in search of food sources (small and equal size settlements).

- 2- Emerge of agricultural growth and markets period; high rate population growth and high rate of growth of cities besides obviously increasing in economic growth rate and stable growth of the urban settlements.
- 3- According to Bryant and Coppak, analysis of development of "city-region", based on evolution theory, the urban form defines as monocentric, an economically dependent on the main city (Jayson, 2006, p. 28-29).
- 4- The city-region developed through the urban expansion using the population growth towards the margins and when rural-urban migrations happened, the Suburban and new roads emerged as a result of continuous city economic attraction.

5.1.2 The relation form between the rural and the city

The city characterized in this phase depended on the rural which was least interacting with the city. It never reached full depending on the city production. Rural agricultural products were essential for the city which could not dispense them, at the same time the city's markets represented the basic needs for the rural but were a minor importance, and easily replaced: In return, the city supplied crafts to rural areas. Rural artisans depended on raw materials from the city. They used these materials in their industry. Direct rural people depended on the city at this phase, cities were a secondary role to the rural. Cities absorbed many farm surpluses.

5.1.3 City-regions patterns:

- Regions with a natural unit: in this case, the boundary between the city-region and another was a natural border .
- Regions with an economic unit: there is the economic integration between human and natural resources, and in this case, the city-region can become Self-sufficient.
- Monocentric urban regions: it depends mainly on the city and there is any urban agglomerations play a role with the main city.

5.1.4 The intellectual and theoretical directions determine the city-region

The simplicity of the economic relationships between the city and its surroundings and the extreme influence of the city depends on the ability of the Beasts to move from city to another area consequently we can determine the city-region through:

- **The natural determination** depended on a set of natural elements which stopped the city influence after that emerge new influence range for another city, also the

natural limits restrict the region and its urban influence besides its effect on population characteristics, activities, needs and functions (Mohamed, 1998).

- **The existing economic interaction relationships:** the mutual trade between the city and the adjoining region which known as economic relationships.
- **The social ties:** the spread of tribes and families and marriage relations besides the religious relations.

Most of the theoretical Attempts tried to explain the form of the areas around the city, but the most came from an economic perspective like the following:

- a- The isolated city-region in von Thünen logic, which could not be Expressed about the recent city-region, but it's one of the earliest attempts to define the city-region on basis of a circle divided into economic sectors.
- b- The Sector theory held illustrated form for the areas around the city on a shape of sectors started from the city as a center and their differ in the proximity and distance due to the economic function for land use in each sector.

5.1.5 The economic functions in the city-region:

The regional service function: centrality was the nature of regional services; it could not be scattered and dispersed when located in central high access places, when services centrality became highly needed to locate in the biggest cities and highest centrality and no doubt central cities were a fortress to keep itself from military invasions.

The administrative function of the city: the administrative function by its nature was a regional function which take into account the scales of the functions and administrative institutions, where representatives of the governor and the leaders of the army, the priests, the main library and the school functioned (Ali, 1988).

The commercial function: the mutual interaction between rural and urban central market resulted in regional integration happened through collections, exchange and distribution of goods in both retail and wholesale market plus the business center.

Taking into account the city effect on the direct agricultural productive sector:

The link between rural and urban zones resulted in exchange of manufactured and processed products; each side sending market products to the other side. Rural areas provided plenty of raw materials needed for industrial production in urban areas, in the form of mineral and agricultural commodities, in addition to rural areas provided most of the food Consumed by the city dwellers (UN, 2003).

5.1.6 The capacity concept of the city-region

The concept of the capacity was limited to the sufficient agricultural production for the total population to avoid the starvation or selling the surplus to urban areas for exchange with other goods; lower level of pollution and primitive methods of transportation were the hallmark of rural gains. The absence of transportation resulted in low rate of rural people migration to the urban regions which helped the low of population density in the city plus the frequency of wars and invasions reduced the population growth rate.

On the other hand, the capacity depended on the ability of the city to hide its population within city walls by using the storage of goods and grains, which prepared for wars and embargo periods and often the city population number is matched with its capacity and ability to protect its population.

5.2 Sustainability of city-region during industrialization stage (beginning of complexity and expansion)

This stage was marked with different sub-phases. The pressures became more on the developmental sectors and many problems arose. These would be explained in the following parts:

5.2.1 The form of city-region

City markets stage: the diffusion of factories and appearance of various products, led to the emergence of major markets. It was possible to serve these markets in the city-region or other city-regions; in the first case, these cities must have large population those were in central location with its surrounding settlements. Then these rural people could access easily from outside to the city. These must be in high spatial centralization and around the points of roads interchange and railways traffic which sprang up after the emergence of the steam engine.

The markets of external cities must be linked with sea or river ports and linked ports which were located on nodal sites at the regional level.

Thus, market cities were characterized by the large size of population and appearance of the immigration streams with high rates of population growth and increase in pollution levels and pressure on the infrastructure facilities of these cities.

With more support for those cities, whatever industrial or markets cities obviously emerged **the stage of the first city:**

With the growth of the urban population to faster rate and speeding up the rate of economic growth due to enter of the industry and multiple transportation (railway, network sand roads) appearance here the first city which dominant on all settlements, consisted of many activities that were concentrated inside, such as banks and business centers; these were found at all roads and transportation networks were necessary around population concentration. Social and administrative organizations is clustered near to markets Caste discrimination disappeared with a high growth rate of population and business activities.

According to Bryant and Coppak, analysis of "city-region" development evolution theory appeared along the second stage of city-region evolution and it became economic, social and environmental coherent unit (Jayson, 2006, p. 29-30).

In this stage, the polycentric urban pattern through the urban expansion process and continues migrations plus directed investments appeared. This system emerged through small and medium cities around the main city; but the main city remained still as the basis of the process supporting functions, Services and employments.

In addition to the emergence of the suburbs around the main city, which was considered as the recipient of increasing city influence and urban dominance and increasing the pressures on its developmental sectors.

5.2.2 The relation form between the rural and the city

The development of the city had a significant impact on reducing the size of the rural, while rural life transformed into new pattern related to new economic concepts. This stage was marked by the decrease of population dramatically in the countryside. Rural became a place to expel people while the city became a place of attraction for migrant workers from the countryside.

Relations have become more complex and more exchanged and turned to be deeper. The relationships not only is one direction between city and rural, but is a two-way between urban and rural areas as well. The rural areas in another side themselves led to a change in size and some rural settlements have developmental roles.

5.2.3 City-regions patterns:

Small and medium city-regions: these regions were characterized, with easily identified boundaries and there was no significant overlap with other cities leverage ranges.

Industries spread in most countries and their concentration in certain regions led to emergence of a new pattern known as **Problem regions**. These regions needed

developmental interventions due to deficit sectorial development on city-regional level or defect in the degree of developmental sectors or weakness to exploit its resources and capabilities or manifestations of certain development issues such as poverty, unemployment and the poor condition of the Built Environment and other developmental problems.

5.2.4 The intellectual and theoretical directions to determine the city-region

With the multiplicity and complexity of economic relations, human intervention was necessary to set limits to define the distinct regions and here appeared **the human Region**. Through these limits, it was subjected to the processes of different regional development planning. It was the set of sustainability measurements in different sectors and the development policies had to be developed based on the possibilities and resources and their characteristics in the regions.

Emergence of different relations between the city and the rural communities (Ali, 1988. P. 219):

- The social interaction called the daily work trip between the city and its surrounding rural regions multiplied in geometrical proportion.
- The city changed of land use in the rural regions surrounding it and many aspects of relationships underwent changes and expressed in statistical methods.

The theoretical directions to determine the city-region:

The industrialization stage was divided into two phases:

The first phase: simple theories to explain the urban features like Theory of G. Chabot and theory of Victor. Gruen and sectors theory and Multiple - Nodules theory.

The second phase: came in the context of the expansion of the city-region and increasing control over settlements around the main city besides increasing pressures and migration rates, those attempts came as the following:

- Trying to explain the spatial distribution of cities to understand the relationship between its size and spacing by Walter Christaller 'central places theory'.
- Economic relations of the market area in the urban center and its geographical space and the most important example was Loach network which depended on the basis of determining the city areas from similar functional specialization.
- Dickinson believed that the study of trade relations between the city and its surrounding countryside relied on the force to attract retail buyers outside the city

and this relationship was directly proportional to the city population, but it decreased as you went away from the city, and disappeared (Amin, 1989).

- Smiles mentioned the functions which controlled the city. These economic functions or social functions were associated with the services which the city specialized. These functions were education, health, culture and entertainment, as those could rely on the road network and transport ways to the city-region (Ali, 1988. p. 220).
- Emergence of the idea of identifying the daily working trip to determine the boundaries of city-region and confirmed that the perfect work trip was 30 km or 30 minutes or maximum of an hour (Ibrahim, 1993).
- The emergence of some statistical methods to determine the theoretical boundaries of the city-region was propounded by the interaction theory.

5.2.5 The economic functions in the city-region:

Subsequently, the industrial city-region obviously resulted in environmental problems. And urban and economic pressures on the city-region (Ali, 1988. p. 65-88):

Traditional industrial cities played the role of rural industrialization and use of rural raw materials. Some rural raw materials were used in the urban industries to manufacture the agricultural inputs.

Specialized industrial cities here, the cities preceded the rural settlement and interacted functionally with them, the industries began in the specialized cities, and the industrialized specialization, transformed the settlements to play the role of assembly line and industrial regional system appeared. Each settlement was partial manufacturing area. All assembled around the main city of the region.

5.2.6 The capacity concept of the city-region

Because of the spread of huge factories and polluting atmosphere and by looking to the growth range of the urban areas, the cities and towns used enormous amounts of materials and produced the bulk of contaminated substances. The intensive nature of human settlements within the industrial cities, and the consumption of more natural resources, the land area was required for housing, as well as economic activities and transport routes. Unfortunately, the land allocated for those purposes was often the best agricultural land.

The urban expansion created a growing demand on the natural resources which often accommodated with sources within rural areas. Most of the times, the disposable waste generated in the city was in the proximity of rural areas. Thus, rural areas became urban

waste sinks, which did not improve the management which led to contaminated water sources in particular and the whole ecosystem.

The rural areas were linked with the cities demographically, with circular long-term migration, resulting in unsuccessful attempts to reduce rural-to-urban migration and control the density of major main cities.

5.3 Sustainability of city-region in technological Renaissance stage (complexity and increase of variables)

After the industrial revolution and its changes in the industrial countries, the modern transportation had influenced the urban network, this revolution led to the destruction of the economic imbalance between rural And urban areas and between the city and the surrounding villages and changed the shape of the urban network, featured new urban centers and extinguished some existing centers and other centers were merged to be Metropolitan urban centers (Khaled, 1995).

5.3.1 The form of city-region

In process of urbanization, some regions registered faster rate of growth. This resulted in development of larger urban centers called "Metropolitan cities", which is not one city but is a group of cities complement each other's where economic activity complementary to itself, the advantage of this phase density of the population is above normal, and provides in it the transportation and exclusive special features such in trade and industry, some of these cities become capital of the main region or the country and become the main center of the government, plus all aspects of social, economic and political activities concentrated in it, so it become obviously "a big city".

The third phase of evolution theory emerged that the city-region depend on shift some activities away from the main city to develop a regional communities' system besides the multiplicity of population activities which shows Near to suburbs and main points around the city because of lower land prices and low taxes, addition to proximity and easily linked to the city.

Consequently, the extended metropolitan region appeared, which were larger than the previous city-regions and the settlements were still trending towards clusters of specialization and emergence of nuclear urban centers. Still, Polycentric pattern or poly-nuclear were existing in the urban form of the city-region (Jayson, 2006, p. 30).

With the complexity of the city region changing their internal relations and the urban content of the city-region appear clearly where it **consisted of three main zones** emphasizes spacing of its ranges and increasing the economic, environmental and urban pressures on the city-region resources(Jayson, 2006, p. 33-34);

The first zone: the city built-up area and the areas of the city edges, it could be divided according to the population size and density to the three areas as follows: concentrated city, inner fringe and the outer fringe.

The second zone: the areas around the city which called urban shadow or Pre-urban it contained from the suburbs and the semi-urban areas, which were far from the city center and could be reached in an hour.

The third zone: it's the Rural Hinterland which considers the furthest zone of the main city.

5.3.2 The forms of relation between the rural and the city

Figure 1 the forms of relation between the rural and the city in pre-industrialization and industrialization stage.

Source: own work.

There was an urban relationships between the dominant city and the other cities at the regional level, because of this kind of relationships, the city grew because external relationships outside its region as a result of being a regional service centers from high level, resulting a rural/rural relationships because of the influence of the city on the its surrounding countryside (Up-down relations) and getting those relationships in this pattern and develop rural centers at the expense of other rural centers without consideration for the administrative role.

5.3.3 City-regions patterns:

Firstly: regions matching with the administrative boundaries; it was possible to match city-region boundary with the administrative boundaries which was drawn by the authorities; in this case, it was easy to collect the information and execute the plans to develop the city-region.

Secondly: the city-regions were classified into two types:

- Planning regions: those regions were taken up for developmental program by the developmental authorities; development rates were faster.
- Problems regions; those regions faced multiple problems and lot of pressures on the economic, social and urban sectors; these led to the decrease of per capita in social and urban service and low per capita income among inhabitants.

Thirdly: The city region could be classified in terms of the development level(Mc Gee, 2007):

- Local city-regions: it had no developmental activities and it served only the surrounding rural and often single-core region.
- Regional city-regions: those regions witnessed the development of their economic and service activities. They played the main role on the larger regional level and often, in this case, be multiple-core regions.

5.3.4 The intellectual and theoretical directions to determine the city-region

- Determine the area of the cities effectiveness in their regions based on the important services rendered to the surrounding rural area by counting the visitors to the city to obtain the regional services by using statistical methods, the most sectors which show the features of the real interaction were the educational, health, business services, and employment opportunities, plus dependence on the movement of buses.
- The most important attribute in determining the city-region was reduced city influence far away from it; this influence was clearly on the direct rural, and the influence become less by distance until it disappeared and it became at exact point zero impact. So residents in this regions deal with another city in order to obtain the regional services.

5.3.5 The economic functions in the city-region:

With continued high pollution levels caused by manufacturing processes, many countries realized they need to move towards less polluted economic sectors and enter the city-

regions in other new activities which specialize economically, and here emerged the tourist city-regions and service city-regions, as example, but when we look at these regions we find:

- New regions or regions the urban development precedes the rural.
- Cities and tourist resorts which became a regional service center for touring hinterland.

5.3.6 The capacity concept of the city-region

This stage witnessed maximum levels of the pollution and emerging regional and global environmental issues. The most major industrial cities, in particular, became consumed a large part of its urban capacity resulting in significant pressure on the environmental and ecosystem within the city-region; the effect was excess utilization the normal limits in terms of consumption of natural resources and environmental disruption, which require new mechanisms to monitor these drawbacks and address these problems. So, the city-regions should have used the sustainable planning not only in the city-regional level but with the administrative approaches together with the broader strategies of sustainable development (UN, 2003).

This thought emphasizes the role of environmental management to preserve the capacity rates under control and environmental management tools would look close linkages between urban and rural areas, and prevent unfair environmental consumption of natural resources, exposing it to decay.

6. City-region in era of new regionalism (stage of extensive complexity and fast variables)

6.1 The form of city-region

Global City Regions; Changed the form of global city-region to turn the development on corridors or a group of urban settlements formed within the city-region and was often referred to as the global city-regions. Because, the strength of the global connection and knowledge-based industries which enjoyed a large movement of people, goods and capital and increased the competition on the industrial sites (Kidokoro et al., 2007, p. 6).

Increase the competitiveness of the global city-regions depending heavily on the settings of regional support, such as established institutions and increase the abilities for planning, research, and development (Marques, 2001). It was possible to merge several cities across multiple states' borders to be major economic blocs, like the countries of East Asia.

Besides the continuing of the previous forms of the city-regions, as in the old regional stage but some regions, especially the regions of major cities continued to grow in an unplanned

and led to continued pressure and due to the emergence of the city-region great complexity of the relations occurred between the city and the settlements in its peripheral. This phenomena could be into two phases, namely:

Realistic stage already happened, namely the Megapolis:

At this stage the cities and urban areas around the Megapolis grew and turned into a huge urban space and the rate of urbanism was rapid.

A nearly Total Urbanization stage, which did not occur yet where the mother city spread, and decomposes around the original city, and created merged new areas, and there was no old model, but looked like a new tape of coherent urban tissues, and it was difficult to imagine because of its absence.

Based on the analysis of Bryant and Coppak, emerged the fourth stage where the pattern became one major city connected to the major cities. And the suburbs merged with the major city. At the same time, the urban growth linked with the neighboring city through the corridors and the highways (Jayson, 2006, p. 31-32).

6.2 The relation form between the rural and the city

Appearance of specialized rural areas paved way for continuously supported the urban economic needs. Such trends needed approval of administrative machineries and legal framework. Around some cities rural areas introduces farm activities which led city agro-industries. The consequential effect of this was the increase in regional GDP. People's standard of living improved. The infrastructure began to develop in commensurate with this trend.

6.3 City-regions patterns:

Can classify the city-regions into:

Mega city-regions: the region which arises from the existing city with the highest population size and urban areas extended and developed to include many suburbs and semi-urban zones; this city-region became complex and there were many aspects and variables and characteristics such as increased immigration rates to these cities.

The polycentric city-region and in this case, it's composed of a group of urban or semi-urban agglomerations which created relationships and had impacts at the regional level.

6.4 The intellectual and theoretical directions to determine the city-region

The city-regions Classified by using the development level starting from a local, regional or global city-regions:

- **Local city-regions:** the region was determined by frequency of services and activities in the city of the region, besides count multiple traffic density on road network which connect the city and the settlements in periphery.
- **Regional city-regions:** was determined by contributing the city-region in the regional GDP and a network of urban economic relations were at the highest regional level by determining the impact of the region's activities on land use and economic activities on the surrounding urban communities.
- **National city-regions:** this region affected the national economy and its multiple and intertwined range of interactions with other ranges of regional city-regions.
- **Global city- regions:** Besides the above types, this region was determined by the network of global economic relations through trade density in all types plus frequency density of air units and maritime transport in the economic activity, and distinguished the region in the media, culture and arts, research centers and universities.

6.5 Requirements of city-regions development in globalization:

As a result of low level of sustainability of the city-region and because of countries needs for to global competition, there was urgent need to improve the sustainable development and sustainability on city-region level. Preparing it for global competition (Ahmed, 2002; Mounir, 2010).

6.5.1 Urban requirements:

- Support the city-region with the basic information to attract the global investments.
- Support the city-regions which have regional ports with the technical innovations centers and support also its abilities to attract the cultural and economic activities.
- Develop the infrastructures in the city-region to maximize the production to achieve economies of size to reduce the cost and linking deprived regions of the coastal ports with regional and global trade corridors.
- Strengthening of competitive city-regions with urban elements of modern communication and recent information (such as satellite stations and global financial centers).
- Rehabilitation of city-regions by developing indicators to monitor sustainable development in these regions and observe the urbanization process that may occur in an unorganized form.

- Integrating economic effective urban conglomerates in the framework of urban capacity and the environmental threshold of resources and activities to strengthen the regional activity and attract investments and employment.
- Prescribe strict standard to limit the overlapping of regional land use between urban and rural areas within the context of the direct investment of urban range.
- Pushing the developmental efforts to rehabilitate the less developed city-regions which have the capacity for development, it would pay to achieve national strategy towards reducing the regional disparities and restore the lost balance.
- Strengthening city-regions with superhighways to link between the center and the periphery of the productivity unit like rapid roads and high-speed communication lines and flow of information factors.
- Rehabilitation of the city-regions through planning the municipal / productivity relations "Logistic Industrial Centers" between the center and the main periphery zones "Minor urban agglomerations" to meet the requirements of international investments to attract more of them to ensure sustained development in the Region.

6.5.2 Economic requirements:

- Increasing the investments' area in the technology industries and the software industry to ensure the global competition.
- More direction towards the sustainable and green economy in all economic sectors to ensure the continuity of economic structure.
- Activate the role of small and medium size companies to shape economic agglomeration which would go into regional and global corporations.
- Set a national plan to invest in the economic resources to increase the benefits of the resources under the limits of environmental capacity.
- Reliance on attracting the Labor-intensive industrial activities and direct capital to ensure sustained operation of economic sectors.
- Support the small and medium industries with the new technology.
- Support the regional urban centers with financial services which were the basis to attract global investments.
- Rehabilitate the potential city-regions to compete and strengthen the economic-industrial network relations to facilitate their merger with the global economy.

- Choose the industrial and economic activities which fitted to attract the foreign investments and provided the suitable economic environment.
- Don't impose and constraints on the directed Foreign investments.

6.5.3 Environmental requirements:

- Set strict environmental instruments and requirements on the polluted imported activities.
- Use the distinct environmental zones in the city-regions to attract the health care activities and global tourism activities under the limits of sustainability and environmental capacity for those zones.
- Determine the goals and values to measure the sustainability in each region to guarantee the sustainable environmental development.
- Set strict environmental conditions to control the fast urban growth, which generated at the expense of agricultural and natural areas in city-regions.

6.5.4 Social requirements:

- Increasing the scientific support for the researchers and scientific institutes.
- Activate the role of the private sectors and the NGOs in the social regional issues.
- Provide training courses to improve the technical abilities of the community and to ensure provide clever employment.
- The effective work to protect the social infrastructure against the negative effects which might be generated due to exposure of closed social environments.

6.6 The economic functions in the city-region:

The city-regions maintained the service function initially; but with the changes in the quality of these services due to the influence of electronic networks the administrative services did not become the basis; but they had become a financial and cultural services besides the functional services which provided in city-regions.

Besides, depending on the city-region on functional specialization, there were tourist city-regions and cultural city-regions which existing on the cultural, scientific and political conferences. There were healthy city-regions which enjoyed the private nature and had stunning views, and they developed over a long period and were not existed at local but national level, some of them were most unique and influential on the global level.

There were city-regions with highly specialized and had unique in environment and the purity of airspace; these regions specialized in all kinds of software technology and

production of electronic pieces and production of micro and precision chips. These regions were placed at the highest in the developmental level.

6.7 The capacity concept of the city-region

The spread of the global mega-city led to huge pressures on the capacity of the city-regions as a result of the continuing migrations from the rural areas to the city. Therefore, it resulted in urban poverty and deterioration of the urban environment. Nearly settlements also suffered from its impacts and exhausted natural resources and potentials of the region (UN, 2003).

Continuation of deteriorating capacity at the city-region resulted in the return of migration. So, some families migrated back to their rural homes.

A unique phenomenon was ruralization of urban employment, the rural labor living in cities and frequented to nearly rural areas during harvest seasons.

Although most of these manifestations might have to ease the pressures on the urban areas and reduced the surplus eventually led to the ruralization of population of the urban areas. That had a long-term negative impact on the economic sectors of the city and to its economic development. But there was a pattern of sustainable regional development and put developmental policies for each positive and negative manifestations may improve the capacity of the city-region.

7. CONCLUSION

- The city emerged to play a regional role to serve rural settlements in its peripheral range.
- The Industrial Revolution had a major effect on the sustainability of the city-region and appeared the occasional urban ranges and many of the economic and urban theories interpreted the size of this reaction, this stage was considered as the real beginning of the environmental and urban pressures in the region and it increased its intensity by increasing the industrial pollution rates and increasing trade with expanding markets.
- The stage of globalization confirmed the increase of the pressure on the regional resources' capacity and decreased the degree of sustainability as a result of the complexity of regional relations within the region and the multiplicity of its forms and its development policies, which stressed the need for a thought on sustainable regional development.

- The global city-region was affected by the global economic variables and the fast dynamic impact which paved way for the development of various elements of the city-region, it become more vulnerable to economic pressures and speeded up the uncontrolled urban growth. It overlapped the use of land and deterioration of life. So there is no way to implement the thought of sustainable planning.
- The basics of regional relations between the urban centers within the city-region changed in terms of the old regionalism, where hierarchy in the relations between the urban communities was depending on its sizes and hierarchy in distribution of economic and service activities. In the new regionalism, the relationship there was no hierarchy in the relationship and the economic activities become more mobile and other activities. It replaced the unstable activities they were centered inside city-regions or major metropolitan cities due to concentration of infrastructure and some existing services in the major cities.
- It changed the range of Time-space relations in the urban system from the old regionalism; it was effected with civil services sector and traditional economic activities were the engine of the urban range and considered the means of transportation were the main effective element in the timing range and urban centers distribution within the urban system. While in the new regionalism, technological services sector and advanced industrial activities were the engine of the urban range at this stage and were the most important influences on distribution of roles and the relationship between the settlements within the urban network.
- Interaction pattern in urban areas changed the old regionalism. The urban centers depended on the activities of services and frequent range of the industrial and economic activities within the range of interaction and thus no change in these ranges had rapidly happened. It resulted in, instability of these ranges; but it changed the distribution and level of services or the spatial use by different activities. But, in the new regionalism the provision of economies moving time range to another between the urban communities which eligible to receive these provisions resulting unstable interaction ranges affected by the vulnerability of the regional economic changes and has become a communication and transportation technology mainly control the spacing of these ranges and its complexity.

- The Hierarchy of urban system changed in the old regionalism to become an urban network in the new regionalism.
- The city-region in the old regionalism was static where it was a few variables with quasi-static border while its shift in the new regionalism to become more dynamic and it's was characterized by fast variables and dynamic border and had a global role in attracting economic, industrial and commercial activities and attracted international investments (FDI).
- The city region planning process became a flexible strategy faced with fast variables and it followed common approach between bottom-up and top-bottom and this strategy was working to collect the investments to achieve strong social infrastructure. It was required in the strategic plan. During the past, the planning process start from end besides depended on the bottom up approach.
- The city-region became open to include global variables and intellectual posts and research of the neighboring city- regions. It closed boundaries with fixed variables in the old regionalism.
- The good governance managed the "system-requirements" within the region after government was present. It provided the projects to fill the gaps.
- City-region was interested in integration and interactive relationships between development sites and their input in the social, urban, economic, and environmental sectors.
- The city-region could move from the developmental level to another higher or lower level. The acquisition of region on the elements of regional and global competition continued eternally.

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